

Improved Discriminatory Ability using Hybrid Feature Selection via Approach Inspired by Grey Wolf Search and Ensemble Classifier for Medical Datasets

Waheeda Almayyan

Computer Information Department, College of Business Studies, PAAET, Kuwait

Abstract- Medical datasets inevitably suffer from redundant and irrelevant attributes, which reduce data mining algorithms' ability and often lead to uninterpretable results. Therefore, the first step in medical diagnosis problems is to reduce dimensionality. This paper presents a computational method that takes advantage of wrapper subset evaluation with a meta-heuristic algorithm in a two-phase process to improve the classification performance with a group of meta-classifiers. The first phase filters the feature domain using the information gain ratio in an attribute evaluation method. The first layer's output serves as an input feature for the second phase, which uses grey wolf optimization to find the optimal feature space. An ensemble-based classifier scheme was built based on C4.5, RandF, and ForestPA classifiers to obtain the final decision. The proposed method was validated on several medical datasets of the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The results show that the suggested approach yields significant performance improvements in Accuracy performance compared to other classifiers.

Keywords- Data Mining; Feature Selection; Grey Wolf Optimization; Information Gain Ratio; Ensemble Classifier.

1. INTRODUCTION

Applying pattern recognition algorithms for data mining allows for acquiring important information from large-scale datasets [1]. These techniques are extensively used to discover relationships and functional patterns in data. Data mining techniques are successfully applied in many economic, industrial, scientific, and medical fields to handle massive datasets [2]. Therefore, data reduction techniques are mostly required for filtering, ranking priorities, and providing means to detect and isolate redundant features. These algorithms increase the quality of analyses and the success of recognition systems [3].

Medical Data Mining (MDM) involves using algorithms and techniques to automate disease diagnosis and prediction [4]. Numerous algorithms have been suggested in the medical diagnosis literature and investigated on several benchmark datasets for cancer, heart disorders, and diabetes. The University of Irvine (UCI) has created a public repository of machine learning databases for this purpose [5].

This study's main objective is to provide an entirely automatic decision-support model to help physicians diagnose diseases by finding the most informative features and maximizing classification accuracy. The proposed approach includes two phases before applying a model learning algorithm, which is expected to enhance the algorithm's exploitation capability. The first phase aims to reduce the number of selected features while keeping high classification accuracy. The second phase adds more informative features to increase classification accuracy. Filter methods are known to give high-quality solutions and are computationally inexpensive and efficient, so we used one of the most popular filter methods: information gain (IG) ratio attribute evaluation in the first phase.

Meta-Heuristics algorithms have recently made significant progress in optimization as they eliminate the drawbacks of conventional search techniques, requiring a high complexity cost [6]. This motivates us to apply the grey wolf optimizer (GWO) algorithm in the second feature selection phase. The GWO algorithm is competitive with other meta-heuristic algorithms such as particle swarm optimization (PSO) and has shown resounding

success in many applications [7]. To increase medical datasets' classification ability, we propose an ensemble-based approach that combines C4.5, RandF, and ForestPA algorithms and relies on a voting mechanism for predicting the classification outcome. Experimental results show that the proposed method seems very promising to be applied for diagnosing disease in the early stages.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Sections 2 and 3 describe the dataset that we have worked on and a review of the literature. Section 4 contains the proposed methodology, followed by experiments and a discussion of the results in sections 5 and 6. Finally, section 6 presents the conclusion.

2. MEDICAL DATASETS

The proposed approach has been tested to predict standard publicly available datasets on diseases that mostly influence the quality of life: the heart-statlog, EEG Eye state, diabetic, hepatitis, lung cancer, and Wisconsin Breast Cancer datasets. The datasets were obtained from the UCI Machine Learning Database Repository [5,8,9]. The details of these datasets are shown in Table 1.

Diabetic Retinopathy Dataset

An experiment was carried out on the Diabetic Retinopathy Debrecen dataset based on extracted features from the Messidor image dataset. The dataset used in this study has 1151 instances, 19 features, and two classes.

EEG Eye State Dataset

Rösler and Suendermann provided the EEG eye state dataset from Baden-Wuerttemberg Cooperative State University, Germany. Electrical waves were recorded from electroencephalogram (EEG) signals for 117 seconds to predict the eyes' state as either open or closed. This dataset includes 14,980 instances and 14 features.

Hepatitis Dataset

The dataset was gathered by the Jozef Stefan Institute, Yugoslavia in 1988 during a study to predict the presence or absence of hepatitis based on several medical test results. This database includes 19 features and 154 instances from two classes (“die” and “live”).

Lung Cancer Dataset

Hong and Young provided the lung cancer dataset in 2006 for predicting lung disease from the results of various medical tests. This dataset includes 31 instances and 56 features from two classes.

Heart-Statlog Dataset

This dataset was donated by The Cleveland Clinic Foundation for heart disease prediction. It contains 269 instances taken from patients and healthy people. This dataset has 13 features and two classes, either '1' or '2', based on the absence and presence of Heart disease, respectively.

Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset

The Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset was collected by Dr. William H. Wolberg from 1989 to 1991 at the University of Wisconsin-Madison Hospitals based on fine-needle aspiration biopsy. The dataset contains 698 instances and nine features.

Table 1
DESCRIPTION OF SELECTED DATASETS

Dataset	Number of features	Number of instances	Imbalance ratio
1. Diabetes	19	1151	1.13
2. Human's cognition state	14	14980	1.22

3. Hepatitis disease	19	154	3.84
4. Lung Cancer	56	31	1.44
5. Heart disease	13	269	1.25
6. Breast Cancer	9	698	1.89

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recently, researchers have begun to consider applying feature selection methods in classification problems. A hybrid machine learning model was proposed by Kaya and Uyar [10] to identify hepatitis based on a rough set and an extreme learning machine. They used a hepatitis dataset from the UCI repository to test their hybrid model. They produced 20 reducts with a range of 3-7 attributes using rough set theory. The reducts were selected first, and then the records with missing values were removed from each one. The classification accuracy obtained using an extreme learning machine was 100% with the reduct of four attributes when using 80% of the training data. The obtained reduct set had only 87 records.

Sartakhti et al. [11] developed a hybrid system using a support vector machine (SVM) and simulated annealing for detecting hepatitis. By removing the missing values, the researchers reduced the size of the dataset to 80 samples. The suggested method was tested with a 10-fold cross-validation procedure, and parameters were tuned for enhancing the classification accuracy. They achieved an accuracy of 96.25%.

A prediction technique for heart disease risk was developed using weighted fuzzy rules [12]. The technique was tested on data from Cleveland, Hungary, and Switzerland. The technique started with removing missing values and grouping instances based on the class label. After discretization, the weighted fuzzy rule was applied to a Mamdani fuzzy inference system. The obtained classification accuracy of 0.51–0.62, 0.71–0.47, and 0.36–0.51 for the Cleveland, Hungarian, and Switzerland datasets. An automatic rough set-based SVM classifier and tested using the Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset [13]. After fine-tuning the SVM parameters, they achieved an accuracy of 100% with five attributes. Vijaya et al. [14] proposed a fuzzy-neurogenetic-based model to predict cardiovascular disease severity and tested it with the Cleveland Heart Disease dataset. They used a trapezoidal membership function for the fuzzification process to train the neural to identify the most significant fuzzy rules. A sigmoidal activation function was applied for both the hidden layer and output layer neurons. They also applied a genetic algorithm to tune the weight associated between nodes. The reported classification accuracy of the system was 88.35%.

Sahan et al. [15] developed a hybrid machine learning method for a fuzzy-artificial immune system with a k-nearest-neighbor algorithm for diagnosis using the Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset. The classification accuracy of the suggested system was 99.4%. Chen et al. [16] proposed an analytical approach by integrating PSO and the 1-NN method to address a liver disorder dataset's feature selection. The correct classification rate of the proposed system with 5-fold cross-validation was 68.99%. Pashaei et al. [17] improved the performance of PSO combined with a C4.5 decision tree by integrating a boosted C5.0 decision tree as a fitness function. The experimental results over five medical datasets from the UCI repository showed that the proposed method improved the performance of PSO and C4.5 and obtained a higher accuracy rate.

Vijayashree and Sultana [18] investigated applying PSO with SVM to proposed a heart disease classification method and reported a classification accuracy of 84.36%. Li et al. [19] suggested a nonlinear transformation technique based on a fuzzy method to find classification information in original data attribute values for a small dataset. They used an SVM as a classifier. The correct classification rate of the proposed system was 70.85% for

the Liver Disorder dataset. Antal and Hajdu [20] proposed an ensemble-based method for identifying the presence of diabetic retinopathy disease. The proposed system's obtained classification results showed 90% sensitivity, 91% specificity, 90% accuracy, and an AUC of 0.989. Naseriparsa and Kashani [21] applied a Naïve Bayes classifier two-stage classification model for enhancing the classification of lung cancer. The suggested model starts with applying PCA to eliminate irrelevant features. Next, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) resampling technique is considered to handle the imbalanced class distribution.

We have observed that several machine learning models applied several feature selection algorithms to enhance the classification performance for disease diagnostic. We propose a novel method that combines feature selection benefits and an ensemble classifier for enhancing medical data discrimination and detection accuracy. The next section provides more detail on the proposed model techniques.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Feature selection is the process of selecting distinctive features by excluding irrelevant and redundant ones. The reduction of features aims to find the essential feature set. This eventually reduces the processing time and enhances the classification accuracy, particularly in MDM [3]. Medical datasets indeed contain plenty of such attributes, which lower data mining algorithms' efficacy [22]. To increase medical datasets' classification ability, we propose a hybrid filter-metaheuristic optimization-based feature selection approach with a voting mechanism's ensemble of classifiers.

The proposed approach combines IG with GWO to enhance the feature selection process's efficiency and overall accuracy. Consequently, using a reduced number of features would cause the search process to converge faster and make it less expensive. In the first stage, we select features through the IG technique, and in the second stage, we apply the GWO technique to construct a new conceptual vector space based on the reductive feature vector space and discover the important associative relationships between features. Then, we build an ensemble-based model that combines C4.5, RandF, and ForestPA, which relies on a voting mechanism for the final classification decision making.

4.1 Information Gain Ratio (IG) Attribute Evaluation

The IG measure is based on the Shannon entropy to select a test attribute at each node within the C4.5 decision tree algorithm [23]. It measures how precisely the attributes predict a test dataset's classes; then, it assigns the "best" attribute as the decision tree's root. The estimated IG needed to classify a given sample s from a set of data samples C , $IG(s,C)$, is calculated as follows.

$$IG(s, C) = \frac{gain(s,C)}{split_info(C)}, \quad 1$$

$$gain(s, C) = entropy(s, C) - entropy_p(s, C),$$

$$entropy(s, C) = -p(s|C) \log_2 p(s|C) - (1 - p(s|C)) \log_2 (1 - p(s|C)),$$

$$p(s, C) = freq(s|C) / |C|,$$

$$entropy_p(s, C) = \sum_i \frac{|C_i|}{|C|} entropy_p(s, C_i),$$

$$split_info(C) = -\sum_i \frac{|C_i|}{|C|} \log \frac{|C_i|}{|C|},$$

where $freq(s,C)$, C_i and $|C_i|$ represent the frequency of the sample s in C , the i^{th} class of C and the number of samples in C_i , respectively.

4.2 Grey Wolf Optimization Algorithm

The GWO algorithm is a population-based metaheuristic algorithm that was introduced by Mirjalili in 2014 [24]. The GWO algorithm is primarily motivated by the leadership and hunting behaviors of grey wolves in nature, which most prefer to live in a pack. Each pack's average size varies from 5 to 12 wolves with a strict hierarchy, and each wolf in the group has a defined role in the hunting process [25]. Each herd has four foremost ranks that are modeled as a pyramid [24].

The first level in the hierarchy of grey wolves is the pack leader called alpha (α). This level is responsible for decisions about all wolf behaviors. Beta (β) wolves are the second level and are responsible for helping in some decisions for the other wolves in the packs. The third level is the delta (δ) wolves and are responsible for watching the territory's boundaries, protecting the group, hunting, etc. The last level in the hierarchal model is called omega (ω), which is the weakest of the wolves, as it should obey other individuals' orders [26].

The second inspiration of GWO is that wolves are known for their group-hunting strategy to catch prey. The hunting process starts with tracking and chasing the prey, then encircling and harassing until it finally stops moving before attacking. According to the GWO algorithm, the alpha, beta, and delta represent the first, second, third-best solutions. The remaining candidate solutions are regarded as omegas. The wolves can encircle their prey during the hunting process in a manner that can be mathematically modeled as:

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_p - \vec{X}(t)| \quad , \quad 2$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = |\vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D}|$$

where \vec{X} and \vec{X}_p represent the positions of the prey and grey wolf at an iteration (t), respectively. \vec{A} and \vec{C} are coefficient vectors that can be formulated as follows:

$$\vec{A} = |2a \cdot \overrightarrow{rand_1} - \vec{a}| \quad , \quad 3$$

$$\vec{C} = 2 \cdot \overrightarrow{rand_2}$$

where $\overrightarrow{rand_1}$ and $\overrightarrow{rand_2}$ are random vectors in [0,1]. \vec{a} is linearly decreasing from 2 to zero over iterations as follows:

$$a = 2 - t * \frac{2}{iterations} \quad 4$$

The parameter iterations determine the maximum number of iterations. The grey wolf position (X,Y) can be updated according to the position of the prey (X^*, Y^*). The best grey wolf position can be updated by adjusting the vectors \vec{A} and \vec{C} . To mimic the hunting behavior, the alpha, beta, and delta are aware of the potential locations of the prey. As the alpha, beta, and delta indicate the best three solutions, the rest of the wolves update their positions according to the best three solutions (\vec{X}_1, \vec{X}_2 , and \vec{X}_3). This can be expressed as follows:

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = (\vec{X}_1 + \vec{X}_2 + \vec{X}_3) / 3 \quad , \quad 5$$

$$\vec{X}_1 = \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \cdot (\vec{D}_\alpha), \vec{D}_\alpha = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X}| \quad ,$$

$$\vec{X}_2 = \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \cdot (\vec{D}_\beta) \cdot \vec{D}_\beta = |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X}| \quad ,$$

$$\vec{X}_3 = \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{A}_3 \cdot (\vec{D}_\delta) \cdot \vec{D}_\delta = |\vec{C}_3 \cdot \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{X}|$$

When attacking the prey, each wolf updates its position between its current position and the prey's position so that $|A| < 1$. In searching for the prey, the alpha, beta, and delta wolves go away from searching for the prey and converge when attacking the prey. A1 can take random values less than -1 or greater than 1 to force the wolves to diverge from the prey.

4.3 On Ensemble Classifiers

Ensemble learning is a paradigm applied in machine learning where several individual classification base models are trained to solve the same problem. Ensemble methods' primary objective is to achieve more accurate classification rates than a single model usually accomplishes [20]. Ensemble methods try to train multiple learning machines and combine their predictions to obtain better accuracy. This paradigm is decisive in achieving an estimation result with higher stability and accuracy by combining multiple independent classification models [27].

Several algorithms were chosen to build ensemble learning models: bagging, boosting, voting, Bayesian parameter averaging and stacking[28]. Numerous studies have proven that decision trees are very effective methods of supervised learning [29]. Among decision tree algorithms, C4.5 has been widely used in data mining due to its high efficiency in handling continuous, discrete attributes and missing values [18]. Meanwhile, RandF is generally more straightforward and can achieve accurate and robust results than single decision trees [30]. Moreover, ForestPA is a class implementing decision forest algorithm that generates trees with high precision based on the feature space's strength. With its novel weight assignment strategy, bootstrap sampling, and penalized attributes, ForestPA generates highly diverse trees while retaining their higher individual accuracy [31].

4.3.1 C4.5 decision tree Classifier

C4.5 is one of the most widely used decision tree algorithms and is an enhanced version of the ID3 algorithm. Its capabilities in approximating discrete-valued functions robust to noisy data are known for their capabilities, in which the learned function is represented by a decision tree [32]. Moreover, C4.5 can handle missing attribute values, which are very common in medical data [17]. The C4.5 algorithm uses the IG ratio as the default attribute choice criterion to choose the best splitting attributes. This algorithm starts with visiting each node to select an optimal split based on the IG ratio's maximization and assigns it as the root node of a tree. Then, it constructs a leaf intended for all of the probable values. The algorithm's main task is to determine the best proper attribute to partition the data into several classes.

4.3.2. RandomForest (RandF)Classifier

RandF algorithm is a tree-based-ensemble classifier based on a combination tree of predictors where each tree depends on the values of a random vector sampled independently and with the same distribution for all trees [30]. RandF builds a combination of individual base classifiers and accelerates the building speed. Each tree is generated using a random vector sampled independently from the classification input vector. The final classification decision is estimated by collecting the votes from all the trees using a rule-based approach (such as majority voting, product, sum, or Bayesian rules) or based on an iterative error minimization technique through reducing the weights for the correctly classified samples.

4.3.3. Forest by Penalizing Attributes (ForestPA) Classifier

Unlike other algorithms that use a subset of the non-class attributes, ForestPA builds a set of highly accurate decision trees by exploiting the strength of all non-class attributes available in a dataset [31]. Simultaneously, some weight-related concerns, such as the weight assignment strategy and weight increment strategy, are considered to retain individual accuracy and promote substantial diversity. ForestPA is constructed by penalizing attributes that are used in previous trees in a decision forest. An attribute tested at a lower level can influence more logic rules than an attribute tested at a higher level, so ForestPA imposes weights in a systematic way such that an attribute that is tested at a lower level receives a lower weight/higher penalty than an attribute tested at a higher level. Additionally, ForestPA randomly selects the weight of an attribute from the weight range allocated for the attribute's level.

4.3.4. Voting Mechanism

Voting is one of the most common intuitive ensemble combination techniques and performs decision-making based on combining several classifiers' outcomes. The decision-making applies a combination rule using the power of several individual classifiers [20,28,32], such as the minimum, maximum, majority, product, and average of probabilities. To obtain the final result in this study, every prediction is subjected to voting to decide the final prediction decision. Consider C target classes testing instance x_t . Each base classifier (h_j) provides a prediction Y_j for testing instance x_t for the target class.

a. Majority Voting rule

According to the majority rule, all classifiers will vote on the class to predict the data, and the class with the most votes will be selected. Majority voting aims to produce a combined prediction for input x , and a binary function can be used to represent the votes:

$$x_t \rightarrow Y_i \text{ satisfy } \max \sum_{i=1}^L \Delta_i(Y_i|x_t) \quad 6$$

$$\text{Where } \Delta_i(Y_i|x_t) = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{if } h_j(x_t) = Y_i \\ 0; & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Later, the votes from all C_i 's classifiers are summed, and the label with the highest vote will be the predicted class. In this case, base classifiers' number and performance play a great role in the ensemble classifier's accuracy [33]. Combining the decisions with majority vote criteria has lower computational complexity and requires much less time overhead.

b. Average of Probabilities

In this technique, classifiers vote on all classes with a vote equal to each class's classification accuracy. For example, if two classifiers classify a problem with 80% and 60% accuracy, then during the voting process, this will assign the two classes to 0.8 and 0.6 votes, respectively. The final decision will be the class with the most significant number of votes. The Arithmetic Average rule is defined as discovering the maximal value of P_j 's arithmetic average ($Y_j|x_t$) as specified in Eq. 7.

$$x_t \rightarrow Y_i \text{ satisfy } \max_{Y_i} \frac{1}{L} \sum_{j=1}^L P_j(Y_i|x_t) \quad 7$$

c. Maximum voting rule

In the minimum or maximum voting rule, probabilities of all classifier's predictions are combined, and a class is assigned based on this value. The maximum rule selects the predicted class label depending on the information provided by P_j 's maximal value ($Y_i|x_t$) across all potential class labels, as specified in Eq. 8.

$$x_t \rightarrow Y_i \text{ satisfy } \max_{v_i} \{ \max_j (P_j(Y_i|x_t)) \} \quad 8$$

5. EXPERIMENTAL WORK AND DISCUSSION

Training and evaluation of models were performed using 10-fold cross-validation, in which nine folds of data are used to train the classifier, and one-fold is used for testing the classifier. This is performed ten times, and accordingly, testing and training encompass all ten folds to prevent a model from being overfitted to the dataset. When learning medical data, measures such as accuracy and the error rate usually favor the majority class [34,35]. To evaluate our approach's feasibility in the medical domain, we applied the 10-fold cross-validation procedure through all the experiments. The selected classifiers' accuracy was calculated using the sensitivity, specificity, balanced accuracy, precision, and *f*-measure, which are more appropriate for imbalanced datasets [36]. The main formulations are defined in Equations 6-10 according to the confusion matrix of a two-class problem.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad 6$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad 7$$

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP+NP} + \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \right) \quad 8$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad 9$$

$$f\text{-measure} = \frac{2 \times TP}{2 \times TP + FP + FN} \quad 10$$

To determine which of the three techniques is the most suitable for the classification problem (C4.5, RandF, or ForestPA classifiers), we start performing classification over the entire dataset. We compared the performance of the suggested ensemble learning model with that of the three classifiers. Results obtained from Table 2 suggest that the ensemble algorithm has the highest values with the diabetic and Lung Cancer datasets, whereas RandF outperformed the other algorithms in the EEG Eye state and statlog heart datasets. However, all classifiers had comparable performance in most cases. Overall, when all features are considered for classification, the balanced accuracy is above 80%.

In the first step, the essential features are identified using the IG-based feature selection method to evaluate the reduced feature subset's reliability. Tables 3 and 4 show the numbers and names of selected features and their classification results from the medical datasets. By implementing IG alone, the approach reduced the dimensionality drastically and eliminated the dataset's irrelevant features by between 14% and 80%. The selection of relevant features by the IG algorithm has significantly enhanced the overall classification performance in most datasets. After the application of IG, the average of balanced accuracy is above 90%. The results show that the

majority-based voting mechanism performs better than the other voting mechanisms in most cases. At this stage, the suggested ensemble algorithm and the other classifiers had comparable performance.

In the second step, to significantly improve the predictive performance, we reduced the first phase using the GWO technique. Then, the remaining features were fed into the meta-classifiers. The pre-step feature selection and comparison of the datasets are shown in Table 5 and Table 6. Adding the GWO algorithm considerably reduces dimensionality and eliminates the datasets' irrelevant features by between 46% and 93%. Notably, the proposed feature selection approach outperforms all other features in every aspect, and the IG-GWO-ensemble approach achieves the highest accuracy rate.

For instance, in the lung cancer dataset, the IG-GWO-ensemble approach outperforms all other individual classifiers and achieves the highest balanced accuracy rates of 91.5%, 90.5%, and 90.5% subsets of 56, 11, and 4 features, respectively. Moreover, the suggested technique helped improve the accuracy rate of the hepatitis dataset by 87.2%, 89.6%, and 88.5% with subsets of 19, 6, and 3 features, respectively. Additionally, classification methods using the three base classifiers obtained excellent results when applied to datasets with imbalanced data distribution. There were no significant performance differences during the second phase regarding the EEG eye state since the features were dramatically reduced.

The IG-GWO-ensemble approach was frequently found to be among the well-performing methods. In many cases, this classifier could handle imbalance very well. IG-GWO-ensemble was consistently the best performing classifier in most datasets. Both RandF and ForestPA tended to yield higher sensitivity, specificity, and precision values, while C4.5 bagging provided better results in terms of the *f*-measure. The performance of the classifiers on different datasets remained almost the same. Overall, the best classifiers performed well regardless of the type of data or the degree of class imbalance.

Table 2
FULL DATASET-COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE UNPROCESSED DATASET (WITH ALL THE ORIGINAL FEATURES)

Dataset	Classifier		Sensitivity	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	<i>f</i> -measure
Diabetic	Ensemble	Maj	0.642	0.704	0.851	0.710	0.674
		Max	0.650	0.687	0.843	0.667	0.701
		Avg	0.653	0.704	0.851	0.677	0.714
	C4.5		0.612	0.680	0.839	0.684	0.646
	RandF		0.637	0.594	0.796	0.640	0.638
	ForestPA		0.653	0.654	0.826	0.681	0.667
EEG Eye State	Ensemble	Maj	0.895	0.948	0.974	0.933	0.914
		Max	0.833	0.870	0.935	0.854	0.839
		Avg	0.864	0.912	0.956	0.890	0.888
	C4.5		0.825	0.861	0.931	0.829	0.827
	RandF		0.907	0.960	0.980	0.949	0.927
	ForestPA		0.867	0.924	0.962	0.903	0.885
Hepatitis	Ensemble	Maj	0.543	0.762	0.872	0.655	0.594
		Max	0.571	0.702	0.843	0.643	0.615
		Avg	0.529	0.714	0.849	0.630	0.607
	C4.5		0.571	0.714	0.849	0.625	0.597
	RandF		0.457	0.798	0.889	0.653	0.538
	ForestPA		0.571	0.762	0.873	0.667	0.615
Lung Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.444	1.000	0.915	1.000	0.615
		Max	0.556	0.909	0.883	0.806	0.714
		Avg	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
	C4.5		0.556	0.909	0.883	0.714	0.625
	RandF		0.333	0.955	0.874	0.750	0.462
	ForestPA		0.333	1.000	0.896	1.000	0.500
Statlog Heart	Ensemble	Maj	0.782	0.867	0.929	0.823	0.802
		Max	0.756	0.833	0.912	0.799	0.783
		Avg	0.773	0.840	0.916	0.810	0.793
	C4.5		0.748	0.820	0.906	0.767	0.757
	RandF		0.773	0.880	0.936	0.836	0.803
	ForestPA		0.765	0.853	0.922	0.805	0.784

Wisconsin Breast Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.959	0.967	0.981	0.939	0.949
		Max	0.934	0.961	0.978	0.951	0.926
		Avg	0.938	0.965	0.980	0.956	0.934
	C4.5		0.934	0.961	0.978	0.926	0.930
	RandF		0.967	0.972	0.984	0.947	0.957
	ForestPA		0.971	0.965	0.980	0.936	0.953

Table 3
SELECTED FEATURES BASED ON IG IN THE FIRST STEP

Dataset	No. Of attributes	Selected attributes	Reduction %
Diabetic	13	3,15,16,4,14,5,9,6,13,7,8,2,1	-30%
EEG Eye State	12	7,6,1,14,13,12,9,10,11,5,8,4	-14%
Hepatitis	6	14,13,12,1,18,5	-68%
Statlog Heart	10	13,3,12,9,8,10,11,2,1,7	-23%
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	8	2,3,6,7,5,8,1,4	-11%

Table 4
PERFORMANCE CLASSIFICATION FOR FEATURE SELECTION BASED ON IG IN THE FIRST STEP

Dataset	Classifier		Sensitivity	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	f-measure
Diabetic	Ensemble	Maj	0.656	0.713	0.856	0.721	0.687
		Max	0.628	0.694	0.846	0.659	0.699
		Avg	0.637	0.712	0.855	0.672	0.715
	C4.5		0.574	0.719	0.858	0.698	0.630
	RandF		0.669	0.713	0.856	0.725	0.696
	ForestPA		0.681	0.643	0.821	0.683	0.682
EEG Eye State	Ensemble	Maj	0.881	0.934	0.967	0.916	0.898
		Max	0.818	0.865	0.932	0.844	0.831
		Avg	0.853	0.898	0.949	0.878	0.872
	C4.5		0.808	0.848	0.924	0.812	0.810
	RandF		0.890	0.949	0.974	0.934	0.912
	ForestPA		0.851	0.910	0.955	0.885	0.868
Hepatitis	Ensemble	Maj	0.500	0.810	0.896	0.686	0.579
		Max	0.486	0.798	0.889	0.656	0.667
		Avg	0.486	0.798	0.889	0.656	0.667
	C4.5		0.443	0.833	0.907	0.689	0.539
	RandF		0.414	0.738	0.859	0.569	0.479
	ForestPA		0.529	0.762	0.872	0.649	0.583
Lung Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.833	0.667
		Max	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
		Avg	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
	C4.5		0.556	0.909	0.883	0.714	0.625
	RandF		0.556	0.864	0.861	0.625	0.588
	ForestPA		0.444	1.000	0.915	1.000	0.615
Statlog Heart	Ensemble	Maj	0.773	0.880	0.936	0.836	0.803
		Max	0.765	0.847	0.919	0.810	0.798
		Avg	0.765	0.853	0.922	0.814	0.805
	C4.5		0.739	0.840	0.915	0.786	0.762
	RandF		0.782	0.867	0.929	0.823	0.802
	ForestPA		0.782	0.867	0.929	0.823	0.802
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.963	0.967	0.981	0.939	0.951
		Max	0.938	0.961	0.978	0.953	0.926
		Avg	0.938	0.965	0.980	0.956	0.934
	C4.5		0.934	0.961	0.978	0.926	0.930
	RandF		0.967	0.969	0.983	0.943	0.955
	ForestPA		0.963	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.947

Table 5
SELECTED FEATURES BASED ON IG-GWO IN THE SECOND STEP

Dataset	No. Of attributes	IG-GWO	Reduction %
Diabetic	5	1,3,7,13,14	-74%
EEG Eye State	1	12	-93%
Hepatitis	3	1,3,4	-84%
Lung Cancer	4	1,2,3,9	-93%
Statlog Heart	7	3,4,5,7,8,9,10	-46%
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	6	1,2,4,5,6,8	-33%

Table 6
PERFORMANCE CLASSIFICATION FOR FEATURE SELECTION BASED ON IG-GWO IN THE SECOND STEP

Dataset	Classifier		Sensitivity	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	f-measure
Diabetic	Ensemble	Maj	0.669	0.674	0.836	0.699	0.684
		Max	0.668	0.687	0.843	0.677	0.707
		Avg	0.664	0.693	0.846	0.678	0.710
	C4.5		0.614	0.696	0.847	0.692	0.650
	RandF		0.674	0.657	0.828	0.690	0.682
	ForestPA		0.678	0.630	0.814	0.674	0.676
EEG Eye State	Ensemble	Maj	0.417	0.761	0.880	0.587	0.488
		Max	0.408	0.764	0.882	0.604	0.584
		Avg	0.415	0.761	0.880	0.605	0.585
	C4.5		0.418	0.760	0.880	0.586	0.488
	RandF		0.368	0.768	0.884	0.563	0.446
	ForestPA		0.420	0.757	0.878	0.585	0.489
Hepatitis	Ensemble	Maj	0.600	0.786	0.885	0.700	0.646
		Max	0.600	0.786	0.885	0.701	0.700
		Avg	0.586	0.786	0.885	0.695	0.695
	C4.5		0.586	0.798	0.890	0.707	0.641
	RandF		0.600	0.786	0.885	0.700	0.646
	ForestPA		0.586	0.786	0.885	0.695	0.636
Lung Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.833	0.667
		Max	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
		Avg	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
	C4.5		0.556	0.909	0.883	0.714	0.625
	RandF		0.556	0.955	0.905	0.833	0.667
	ForestPA		0.444	1.000	0.915	1.000	0.615
Statlog Heart	Ensemble	Maj	0.765	0.900	0.945	0.858	0.809
		Max	0.748	0.887	0.939	0.825	0.840
		Avg	0.739	0.887	0.939	0.822	0.838
	C4.5		0.748	0.887	0.939	0.840	0.791
	RandF		0.739	0.880	0.935	0.830	0.782
	ForestPA		0.798	0.860	0.926	0.819	0.809
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.963	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.947
		Max	0.954	0.958	0.977	0.957	0.924
		Avg	0.959	0.958	0.977	0.958	0.924
	C4.5		0.950	0.959	0.977	0.923	0.937
	RandF		0.963	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.947
	ForestPA		0.967	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.949

Table 7 show that the proposed IG-GWO-ensemble technique performed better than previous studies regarding the EEG eye state, statlog-heart, and lung cancer datasets from the UCI repository. Nevertheless, the classification accuracy on the other datasets was notably enhanced as the number of features was reduced. Tables 3, 5, and 7 show that ensemble values are, for the most part, better than the values of the individual learning models on all five metrics. The results showed an excellent average correctness rate of the studies performed so far on all medical datasets by employing the IG-GWO-ensemble model. Furthermore, due to the subsets' dimensionality reduction, the proposed IG-GWO-ensemble model reduced the time overhead when applied to the feature selection and ensemble model. The results strongly suggest that the proposed IG-GWO-ensemble model could aid in the dimensionality reduction and diagnosis of diseases, and it could be beneficial to physicians for making final decisions about patients.

Table 7
COMPARISON OF IG-GWO-ENSEMBLE AND PREVIOUS RESEARCH RESULTS (ACCURACY IN %)

Author/ Technique	Dataset					
	Diabetic	EEG Eye State	Hepatitis	Lung Cancer	Statlog Heart	Wisconsin Breast Cancer
[11]			96.25%			
[12]					62.0%	
[15]						99.4%
[18]					84.36%	
[37]		96.0%				
[21]	90.0%					

[22]				83.0%		
Full dataset	85.1%	98.0%	88.9%	91.5%	93.6%	98.4%
IG	85.8%	97.4%	90.7%	91.5%	93.6%	98.3%
IG-GWO	84.7%	88.4%	89.0%	90.5%	94.5%	97.9%

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented a method designed for use in diagnosis based on several medical datasets. We have developed a two-step feature selection technique to eliminate non-essential features, which enhanced the classification performance. The GWO algorithm was used for the feature selection process and IG ratio attribute evaluation to optimize the efficiency of the feature selection process and enhance the accuracy of the classification with voting criteria. The results showed that the performance of the ensemble method seems very promising for MDM.

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